

Tracer Study of the School of Education Graduates of San Isidro College: Their Employability and Suggested Interventions

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ABSTRACT

A tracer study is a robust tool that provides beneficial information for evaluating the performance and whereabouts of graduates in their workstations. An academic institution like San Isidro College' School of Education (SED) has for its goal to produce competent professional teachers for Basic Education schools that can ultimately compete in the local, national and international school environment. This study hopes to provide a useful tool in determining the quality of the SED's programs in San Isidro College, vis-à-vis, the graduates' employment status that facilitate in understanding graduates' motivations as contributing factors in finding successful employment opportunities. A total of 90 graduates for the academic year 2016-2017 up to 2018-2019 responded to this study. A structured survey questionnaire served as instrument to gather the data interpreted through frequency and percentages. Results revealed that most of the graduates were females belonging to the 20-22 years old age bracket, single, residents of the city, graduated in the academic year 2017-2018, and major in English. Their first job was in the academe, stayed for one year to less than 2 years, is on contractual status, and working locally. They have a teaching position, receiving a monthly salary of ₱5,000.00 to less than ₱10,000.00 and were connected in the private sector. Their being SED graduates contributed very much to their present job. The survey identified that the possible interventions to improve the employability of education graduates include: on-the-job-training for graduating students, more job counseling for students, and open job search and linkages of the school with other agencies that are work providers.

Subject Area

Tracer Study

Keywords: *Tracer study, Employability*

INTRODUCTION

A tracer study is an important vehicle primarily intended to locate graduates of an academic institution. Some studies track down graduates in order to seek and develop continuous feedback for their Alma Mater. This kind of study is geared to generate or influence decision making and planning of certain institution with regards to the development and improvement of the curriculum. Likewise, it regulates document efficiency and supports the demographic profile of a certain institution that can be measured through the quality of graduates.

It is not surprising therefore that employability and the ‘demand’ of a certain profession are huge factors in the choice of degrees. Consequently, one of the main goals of a higher education institution is also based on the premise that graduates may continually respond to the needs of a highly evolving and competitive ‘market’, as they serve as a ‘factory’, a breeding ground for professionals and employees of industries in the future. This scenario remains an ongoing challenge among education stakeholders in the Philippines. To prove this context, many young professionals shift many times in their jobs because of mismatch and low salaries of the first profession they finished in a university (Rojas & Rojas, 2016).

The study hopes to provide a useful tool in determining the quality of the SED programs at San Isidro College, vis-à-vis, the graduates’ employment status. It also provides relevant information to San Isidro College’s administration and the School of Education to improve the SED programs to be at par with other Teacher Education Institutions’ programs in the country and to meet the demands of the times.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The study aimed to find out what avenues were ventured upon by the School of Education (SED) graduates and how these data can contribute to strengthened the programs at San Isidro College, in the light of the K-12 Education.

This study sought to answer the following problems:

1. What is the employment status of the graduates in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 first job after college;
 - 1.2 the time span stayed in the first job;
 - 1.3 type of present employment;
 - 1.4 place of work;
 - 1.5 position;
 - 1.6 salary; and
 - 1.7 agency employed?
2. What is the extent is the contribution of San Isidro College to the graduates’ present job?
3. What possible interventions can improve the employability of San Isidro College’s graduates?

RESEARCH DESIGN

In ascertaining the status of this tracer study, the descriptive method of research was used. The study employed the descriptive survey which covers the Education graduates from 2016-2019 of

San Isidro College. The respondents of the study were the Education graduates of San Isidro College for the academic years 2016-2017 up to 2018-2019.

A period of one month was spent in the gathering of the data. A researcher-made instrument was used to gather the necessary information in this tracer study. The questionnaire comprised the following: (a) respondent's profile, (b) employment profile and (c) the extent San Isidro College contributed to their present job and possible intervention suggested to improve the employability of San Isidro College graduates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age now, civil status, location of residence, academic year graduated, program, and major field. The result shows that most of the respondents were female, indicating that many of the Education graduates were females. Accordingly, women are considerably over-represented in the teaching profession. Even during enrolment period at San Isidro College, there are significantly higher rates of females than males taking the Education course. The 2020 Global Gender Gap Report of the World Economic Forum (WEF) found that 71.3 percent of women are enrolled in secondary education and 40.4 percent in college, compared to only 60.2 percent and 40.4 percent, respectively, among men (Cruz, 2019).

Table 1. Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of sex, age, civil status, location of residence, academic year graduated, program, and major field ($N=90$).

Demographic Profile			
Age Now	20 – 22 yrs.		
	Demographic Variables	<i>f</i>	%
Sex	Male	25	20.83
	Female	65	54.16
Civil Status	Single	75	62.5
	Married	15	12.5
Location of Residence	City	46	38.33
	Municipality	44	36.66
Year Graduated	2016 – 2017	17	14.16
	2017 – 2018	43	35.83
	2018 – 2019	30	25
Major Field	Values Education	19	15.83
	English	24	20
	Mathematics	9	7.5
	Filipino	8	6.6

It is also revealed from the tracer that the respondents mostly belonged to the age bracket between 20-22 years old upon the conduct of this study. These groups are mostly single and in the prime of their lives.

Moreover, the respondents were graduates at San Isidro College during the academic year 2017-2018 which is 35.83 percent of the total respondents. A good number of these respondents were English majors with 20%, followed by the Religious Education majors with almost 16% while the rest of the majors have a percentage lower than 10%.

Table 2 presents the employment data on the first job that the San Isidro College's SED graduates have. From the list of possible employment sectors, the result shows that most of the

Tracer Study of the School of Education Graduates of San Isidro College: Their Employability and Suggested Interventions

SED graduates have the teaching as their first job after graduation. This means that the education graduates of San Isidro College are equipped in their training as future teachers. This showed their readiness to be in the teaching field. This is evident when they got their first job despite the fact that they are not board passers yet.

Some SED graduates explored the Business Processing Outsourcing (BPO) Industry. These composed almost 8% of the total population of the respondents. There were those who did not give their responses, probably because they cannot find the jobs in the list or maybe they were still searching for a job.

Table 2. Responses of the graduates on their first job employment.

First Job Employment of the Respondents	<i>f</i>	%
Manufacturing	1	1.11
Wholesale and Retail Trade, repair motor vehicles, motorcycles and personal household goods	3	3.33
Electricity, Gas, and Water Supply	0	0
Hotels and Restaurants	0	0
Transport Storage and Communication	0	0
Financial Intermediation	1	1.11
Real Estate, Renting, and Business Activities	0	0
Public Administration and Defense; Compulsory Social Security.	1	1.11
Education	57	63.34
Health and Social Work	0	0
Other community, Social and Personal Services Activities	1	1.11
Private Households with Employed Persons	3	3.33
Others: BPO	7	7.78
No response	16	17.78
Total	90	100

Table 3 presents the duration of the SED graduates in their first job. The result shows that almost 28% stayed in their first job for one year to less than two years. This is followed by those who stayed in their first jobs from seven to eleven months (27%), then by those who stayed in their first jobs from one to six months (23%), giving at most 78% of the total respondents. These findings indicate that they were able to find a much better job after their first job, the reason why they have to transfer in their present jobs. Many of the fresh graduates still have to take their Licensure Examination for Professional Teachers (LEPT) hence, when they passed the board exams, they felt confident and ready to apply in the DepEd or the private schools where they wanted to teach. It could be deduced that their employability as a SED graduate is very good, because they were able to find jobs after graduation despite waiting for their eligibility as a licensed professional.

Table 3. Employability of the Graduates as indicated by the duration in their first job.

How long did you stay in your first job?	<i>f</i>	%
less than a month	1	1.11
1 to 6 months	21	23.34
7 to 11 months	24	26.67
1 year to less than 2 years	25	27.78
2 years to less than 3 years	12	13.33
3 years to less than 4 years	3	3.33
No response	4	4.44
Total	90	100

Table 4 presents the present employment status of the SED graduates for the academic years 2016-2017 up to 2018-2019. The data show that majority of them were on their contractual status which is almost 39% of the total respondents and 24% were in the temporary status. This could be because they were newcomers in their jobs and usually many agencies put their newly-hired employees on probationary for one or two years, until such time when they could acquire eligibility through the civil service examination. However, there were also 23% who immediately were put as regular or permanent in their status. Generally, once the employee passed the licensure examination or the civil service examination they are immediately employed as permanent or regular employees.

Table 4. Respondents' present employment status

Present Employment Status	<i>f</i>	%
Regular or Permanent	21	23.34
Temporary	22	24.44
Casual	2	2.22
Contractual	35	38.89
Self-employed	6	6.67
No response	4	4.44
Total	90	100

Table 5 presents the place of work of the SED graduates for the academic years 2016-2017 up to 2018-2019. The survey shows that 92% of the respondents worked locally or within the province of Bukidnon. These graduates more specifically are connected with the Bukidnon Association of Catholic Schools (BUACS), while two percent are working abroad. There were about 6% who did not respond to this question, probably because they are still making a decision whether to stay in Bukidnon or to work outside Bukidnon or even abroad.

Table 5. Respondents' responses to the place of their work

Place of Work	<i>f</i>	%
Local	83	92.22
Abroad	2	2.22
No response	5	5.56
Total	90	100

Table 6 presents the kind of work position of the SED graduates in their first job. The result shows that 61% are into teaching profession. This means that they are vertically aligned with the degree they graduated from. However, there were 31% who were employed in the non-teaching

Tracer Study of the School of Education Graduates of San Isidro College: Their Employability and Suggested Interventions

position. Since most of these graduates were absorbed by the BUACS, some of them worked in the guidance office, finance office, libraries, registrar’s office, and campus ministry office. Those who were not absorbed by the BUACS were in other fields or in other agencies.

Table 6. Respondents’ responses as to the kind of Work Position they have in their first job

Job Positions	<i>f</i>	%
Teaching	55	61.11
Non-teaching	28	31.11
No response	7	7.78
Total	90	100

Table 7 presents the gross monthly salary of the SED graduates from their employment agencies. The Table shows that almost 36% of the respondents received a salary within the bracket of ₱5,000.00 - ₱ 10,000.00 and 33% have salaries within the range of ₱10,000 to less than ₱15,000. There were 11% who received salaries within ₱20,000 to less than ₱25,000, while 4% have ₱25,000 and above salary range. Considering that most of these are still new to the service and working in private agencies, their salaries are relatively low. Those who were absorbed by the DepEd have higher salaries because the DepEd follow a scheme for salary standardization.

Table 7. Gross Monthly Salary of the graduates employed in their workplace

Monthly Salary	<i>f</i>	%
Below ₱ 5,000.00	7	7.79
₱ 5,000.00 to less than ₱ 10,000.00	32	35.56
₱ 10,000.00 to less than ₱ 15,000.00	30	33.33
₱ 15,000.00 to less than ₱ 20,000.00	3	3.33
₱ 20,000.00 to less than ₱ 25,000.00	10	11.11
₱ 25,000.00 and above	4	4.44
No response	4	4.44
Total	90	100

Table 8 presents the agency where the SED graduates were employed based on the result of the survey. It shows that almost 78% were employed in the private schools, while almost 17% are now connected with the public agency. From the survey, it was evident that the BUACS absorbed many of the San Isidro College SED graduates, indicating that they support the graduates of the Catholic school. This could be because they trust that these graduates have good values education formation and could be trusted in their work. Besides, they could easily get the background of the graduates from San Isidro College. Some of these graduates were also recommended by the President of the college to the particular BUACS school when they scout for new employees.

Table 8. Responses as to what Agency the SED graduates were employed

Agency the SED graduates were employed	<i>f</i>	%
Private	70	77.78
Public	15	16.67
No response	5	5.55
Total	90	100

As shown in Table 9, when the respondents were asked as to the extent that San Isidro College, School of Education’s contributed to their present jobs, more than 63% responded with “*very much*”, 21% responded with “*much*”, and 14% with “*just enough*”. It is evident that about 85% of the graduates indicated that San Isidro College has really contributed in their knowledge and skills

as they worked in their present jobs. Their Baccalaureate degree had honed and prepared them to become professional teachers imbued with the graduate attributes of being disciplined, confident, God fearing, and service oriented.

Table 9. Extent of contribution of San Isidro College to the graduates' present job

Extent of Contribution of SIC to the graduates' present job	<i>f</i>	%
Very much	57	63.33
Much	19	21.11
Just enough	13	14.45
Not much	0	0
None at all	0	0
No response	1	1.11
Total	90	100

After responding to the tracer study, the respondents suggested for some interventions to improve the employability of the SED graduates after graduation. As observed in their responses as to the number of year's gap before they got employed, there were those who were employed two years or more after graduation. This employability gap could be caused by student's lack of confidence in their application for the job, so that, they suggested the intervention of *on-the-job training of graduating students*.

Included in the SED curriculum, are the subjects for experiential learning. These include Field Study are *101- Observation of Teaching-Learning in Actual School Environment; Field Study 102 - Participation and Teaching Assistantship with Action Research, and Ed 112 - Teaching Internship*. These subjects allowed the students to have the actual on-the-job training.

Table 10. Possible Interventions to Improve the Employability of Education graduates

Interventions	<i>f</i>	%
Additional subjects heading to career path	18	20
more on job counseling of students	14	15.56
on-the-job trainings for graduating students	39	43.33
open job search activities	16	17.78
linkages of school with other agencies that are work providers	26	28.89
good marketing strategies	5	5.56

They also suggested more *linkages of schools with other agencies that are work providers*. The teaching internship was done on-campus at the IBED and off-campus at the DepEd schools. In many ways, the experience that they have in-campus and off-campus open avenues for them to be hired in San Isidro College and in the DepEd. The BUACS had more or less 35 schools all over Bukidnon, and the schools are good avenues for the fresh graduates to kick-off in their career. San Isidro College is a member of the BUACS and therefore can establish a good linkage with the private schools connected with BUACS.

The exit conference of the dean and the guidance counselor among the graduating students also, provide job counseling to the students. Probably, some students still need additional trainings to really prepare them for their future career. However, students also have to bear in mind that through actual teaching in their present jobs, they will learn more the craft in teaching. The knowledge and skills in teaching just needs patience, perseverance, and practice.

SUMMARY

This tracer study among the SED graduates tracked the profile of the respondents, their first job, present employment status, extent that San Isidro College had contributed to their present job and the possible interventions to improve their employability. The study revealed some things to be done to improve and enhance what the school has started to do. The SED to develop upgrade and have the skills needed in forming future competent teachers. This tracer study can serve as the beginning of a continuous journey in tracing the SED graduates of San Isidro College.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The School of Education of San Isidro College has productively attained its goal of developing the education students who can provide the learners in the Basic Education the knowledge they need. This is manifested by the high percentage of graduates who landed as teachers in the private and public sectors.

The degree programs that Teacher Education students pursued help them improved their skills and their employment status. These are manifested by the high percentage of respondents whose job at present are highly related to their program of choice.

In a capsule, the tracer was able to track the avenues ventured by the School of Education graduates. The data provided the information on what to strengthen in the SED program at San Isidro College. The findings revealed that the SED graduates are generally satisfied with the delivery of the programs at San Isidro College's School of Education. However, they gave suggestions for the intervention to improve the employability of San Isidro College graduates. They recommend as interventions the following: on-the-job-training for graduating students, more job counseling for students, open job search and linkages of the school with other agencies that are work providers. As a whole, the SED's vision, mission, core values and graduate attributes have cascaded into the SED graduates and prepared them in their future work exhibiting successful teaching employment in both private and public schools.

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